

where $\bar{R}$ = free radical (confirmed by induced polymerisation with acryl nitrile) and $kf \gg ks$

The final rate law thus can be derived as :

$$-\frac{d[V(V)]}{dt} = \frac{2ksK_1K[VO_2 \cdot 2H_2O^+][L\text{-Rhamnose}][H_2SO_4]}{1 + K[L\text{-Rhamnose}]} \dots (4)$$

Due to coordination, the activation energy for C-C bond rupture is lowered¹⁰ and this is in agreement with the observed value of $\Delta H^\ddagger$. Further, the unimolecular disproportionation of complex proposed in step 3 is consistent with the observed small value of $\Delta S^\ddagger$.

Thus, the proposed steps (1-3) and rate law (4) incorporate the kinetic results satisfactorily.

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Potentiometric Determination of Dissociation Constants of DL-Tryptophan in Different Aquo-Organic Solvents

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In continuation of our earlier work on metal-amino acid complexes^{1,2}, this communication reports the dissociation constant (pK) of DL-tryptophan at constant ionic strength in different aquo-organic solvents (20%, v/v) viz., acetone, acetonitrile, iso-propanol, N,N-dimethyl formamide, *n*-butanol and dimethyl sulfoxide by Albert Serjeant³ method.

Experimental

DL-Tryptophan was obtained from BDH and all other solvents were of AnalaR grade. pH measurements were made on a Toshniwal digital pH meter (accuracy ± 0.1 pH) with glass calomel electrode assembly. The temperature of the cell was maintained by a thermostat (U_s -type, German) having an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

For determining the pK of DL-tryptophan (HA) the calculated amount of the HA corresponding to 0.01 M per 25 ml solution is dissolved in 20% solvent and 0.1 M $NaClO_4$ (giving a total volume of 22.5 ml). It was titrated against 0.1 M $NaOH$ in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen and the pH was recorded as equilibrium reached after each addition⁴. The pK values of $\overset{+}{N}H_2CHCOO^-$ group of DL-tryptophan determined in different solvents (20%, v/v) at $25^\circ \pm 0.1$ and $\mu = 0.1$ M $NaClO_4$ are given in Table 1 and follow the order: N,N-dimethyl formamide (9.24) > dimethyl sulfoxide (9.19) > acetone (9.15) > iso-propanol (9.14) > acetonitrile (9.08) > water (9.02) > *n*-butanol (8.96).

This variation in values may be partly due to the change in dielectric constant⁵ of the medium which depends on the viscosity and ionic interaction in solutions⁶.

TABLE 1—THE pK VALUES OF DL-TRYPTOPHAN IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS (20%, v/v) AT $25^\circ \pm 0.1$ AND $\mu = 0.1$ M $NaClO_4$.

Titrant 0.1N $NaOH$ ml	A		B		C		D		E		F		G	
	pH	pK												
0.0	6.75	—	5.70	—	6.48	—	6.54	—	6.50	—	6.96	—	4.60	—
0.5	8.57	9.17	8.45	9.05	8.45	9.05	8.44	9.04	8.87	8.97	8.34	8.94	8.32	8.92
1.0	9.00	9.17	8.98	9.16	8.90	9.07	8.89	9.07	8.86	9.04	8.81	8.98	8.82	8.96
1.5	9.87	9.20	9.82	9.15	9.27	9.10	9.27	9.10	9.28	9.11	9.18	9.25	9.20	9.03
2.0	9.76	9.20	9.72	9.15	9.70	9.18	9.67	9.10	9.70	9.18	9.59	9.02	9.55	8.98
2.5	10.48	9.48	10.45	9.45	10.40	9.40	10.38	9.39	10.48	9.15	10.22	8.91	10.28	8.94
Mean	—	9.24	—	9.19	—	9.15	—	9.14	—	9.08	—	9.02	—	8.96

A = N,N-dimethyl formamide; B = dimethyl sulfoxide; C = acetone; D = iso-propanol; E = acetonitrile;
F = water; G = *n*-butanol.

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pH-Metric Studies on the Copper Benzamidothiosemicarbazide Complex

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INTERACTION between thiosemicarbazide, $\text{NH}_2\text{C}(\text{X})\text{NHNH}_2$ ($\text{X}=\text{O}, \text{S}, \text{Se}$) and $\text{Pb}(\text{II})$ has been reported by Ajayi *et al*¹ and stability constants were calculated by polarographic method. Stability constant and heat of formation of $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$ complex of thiosemicarbazide were determined by Goddard and coworkers². Campbell and Grzeskowiak³ prepared two series of $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ complexes of thiosemicarbazide and elucidated their structure employing ultraviolet and visible spectroscopic technique. In our earlier communication⁴, extensive studies on the interaction of $\text{Hg}(\text{II})$, $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Pb}(\text{II})$ with benzamidothiosemicarbazide in solution and in solid state were reported.

In the present communication, pH-metric results of our studies on the composition as well as the stepwise stability constant and overall stability constant of benzamidothiosemicarbazide (abbreviated as BTSC) complex of $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ have been reported.

Experimental

Benzamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) was prepared by the method described by Verma⁵ and its solution was prepared by dissolving weighed amounts in 80 : 20 ethyl alcohol : water mixture. Fresh solution of BTSC was always used. Stock solution of copper acetate was prepared by dissolving the salt (B. D. H., 'AR' grade) in doubly distilled CO_2 free water. The strength of the solution was determined by the usual method. Fresh solution of aqueous KOH (B. D. H., 'AR' grade) was always used. Elico-pH meter, in conjunction with hydrogen glass electrode and S. C. E. was used for pH measurements. Standard solution of potassium

hydroxide was added to the reagent vessel from a microburette (least count 0.05 ml). All the pH measurements were performed at 29 ± 0.1 using Toshniwal model thermostat

Results and Discussion

Bjerrum's method has certain limitations when applied to aqueous-mixed alcoholic medium with more than 50 per cent alcohol, since the pH-scale set for aqueous medium is not applicable to non-aqueous medium. The values of stability constant determined for these systems would not, therefore, be the real values but would be the apparent ones. But here, since the studies were carried out in alcohol-water mixtures with more than 50 per cent water, the stability constants determined may be taken as real values.

The pK value (8.1) of BTSC determined pH-metrically, was in close agreement with the value obtained by polarographic method⁶. pH-metric titrations performed with mixtures of metal-ligand, ligand and metal separately against 0.1 M KOH showed lowering of pH, proving liberation of H^+ ions as a result of complex formation. Maximum lowering of pH in the case of 1 : 2 Cu -BTSC mixture and the inflection corresponding to 2 moles of KOH : 1 mole of copper acetate indicated 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio in the complex.

pH-metric titration of BTSC alone and in the presence of different concentration of Cu^{2+} ions performed according to the method recommended by Calvin and Melchoir⁷, gave typical pH-metric curves when titrated against standard KOH . From these curve at various values of pH, a set of $\bar{n}$ values was determined and the concentration of free ligand ($\bar{A}$) was calculated. The values of $\bar{n}$ were plotted against the corresponding values of pA or $-\log(A)$. As a first approximation the value of pA at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and at $\bar{n}=1.5$ are equal to $\log K_1$ (3.703) and $\log K_2$ (3.037) respectively. The overall stability constant ($\log K$) came to be 6.740.

These temporary constants were corrected by Bjerrum's method⁸ of successive approximation. The value of spreading factor 'x' was found to be 1.0765 and the corrected values of formation function ($\bar{n}$) for each corresponding value of ($\bar{A}$) were then plotted against $-\log(A)$. The final values of $\log K_1 = 3.85$, $\log K_2 = 2.90$ and overall $\log K = 6.75$ were obtained.

From the results it is clear that $\bar{n}$ increases with the increase in pH showing thereby that it is the anionic form which takes part in the reaction.

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